

TABLE 2—INFRARED SPECTRAL BANDS (cm⁻¹) OF TATSC AND ITS COMPLEXES AND TENTATIVE ASSIGNMENTS

TATSC (L)	Co(L ₂)	Ni(L ₂)	Cu(L ₂)	Zn(L ₂)	Cd(L ₂)	UO ₂ (L ₂)	Assignment
1 650	1 630	1 625	1 630	1 620	1 625	1 630	C=N stretch ^a
—	1 590	1 600	1 580	1 590	1 585	1 590	C=N-N=C stretch ^b
1 540	—	—	—	—	—	—	N-C-N stretch ^c
1 460	—	—	—	—	—	—	C=S stretch ^d
1 320	—	—	—	—	—	—	NH-C=S stretch ^e
1 030	1 050	1 045	1 050	1 045	1 045	1 050	N-N stretch ^f
810	—	—	—	—	—	—	C=S stretch ^g
—	720	725	715	720	720	725	C-S stretch ^h
—	455	460	455	460	470	455	M-N stretch ⁱ
—	290	280	275	280	290	285	M-S stretch ^j

^a Ref. 7. ^b Ref. 11. ^c Ref. 12. ^d Ref. 13. ^e Ref. 14. ^f Ref. 15. ^g Ref. 16. ^h Ref. 17. ⁱ Ref. 6. ^j Ref. 17.

in the stretching frequency of C=N in the ligand observed in the complexes also indicates the involvement of azomethine nitrogen in complexation and is supported by a positive shift of 15–20 cm⁻¹ in the N-N stretching frequency of TATSC when it coordinates with the metal ions. Appearance of new bands due to M-N and M-S stretching vibrations in the spectra of the complexes further supports coordination of the metal ion to the bidentate ligand through azomethine nitrogen and thio sulphur.

Thermogravimetric studies indicate that the metal complexes do not contain any water and that they are thermally quite stable. Decomposition started at relatively higher temperature and was complete above 680° (Table 1). The thermal stability of the complexes were in the following order for metal ions, UO₂^{II} > Ni^{II} ~ Zn^{II} > Co^{II} > Cu^{II} ~ Cd^{II}.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to Prof. Arun K. Dey for his kind interest in the work, and thank U.G.C., New Delhi, for financial support.

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Stability Constants of some Bivalent Metal Ion Chelates of Schiff Bases derived from 2,4-Dihydroxybenzaldehyde

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Manuscript received 19 February 1986, revised 17 June 1986, accepted 25 June 1986

POTENTIOMETRIC studies have been carried out on metal chelates of UO₂^{II}, Cu^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Zn^{II} with 2,4-dihydroxybenzylidene thiosemicarbazone and 2,4-dihydroxybenzylidene phenylhydrazone. The proton-ligand and metal-ligand stability constants have been determined by the Calvin-Bjerrum pH titration technique as adopted by Irving and Rossotti¹, at 30±0.1° and ionic strength 0.1 M in 75:25 (v/v) dioxan-water medium.

Experimental

The two ligands (A) 2,4-dihydroxybenzylidene thiosemicarbazone and (B) 2,4-dihydroxybenzylidene phenylhydrazone were synthesised by refluxing equimolar quantities of 2,4-dihydroxybenzaldehyde and the respective amines in ethanol. The products were repeatedly crystallised to obtain analytically pure samples. The purity was tested by tlc and elemental analysis (Table 1).

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL, AND PHYSICAL, DATA OF LIGANDS

Ligand	Molecular formula	M p.	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		
			C	H	N
(A)	C ₉ H ₉ N ₂ SO ₂	234°	45.40 (45.46)	4.27 (4.30)	19.96 (19.90)
(B)	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₂	164°	68.20 (68.39)	5.28 (5.30)	12.31 (12.28)

A Corning 12 pH meter was employed throughout the investigation for pH determination. The glass electrode supplied was used in combination with a dip type calomel electrode. The meter has a temperature compensator which covers a range of 0 to 50°. Standardisation of pH meter was resorted to by using buffers of 0.05 *M* potassium hydrogen phthalate (pH 4.019 at 30°) and 0.01 *M* borax (pH 9.18 at 30°).

The metal solutions were prepared by using A.R. grade salts and were standardised by complexometric titrations with EDTA²⁻, and UO₂^{II} was estimated gravimetrically³ as U₃O₈. During the titration, oxygen-free nitrogen, pre-saturated with solvent mixture was bubbled through the solutions.

The following solutions were titrated potentiometrically against standard NaOH solution (1.09 *M*): (i) 5 ml of 0.16 *M* HClO₄ + 5 ml of 0.64 *M* NaClO₄ + 30.0 ml of dioxan, (ii) 5 ml of 0.16 *M* HClO₄ + 5 ml of 0.64 *M* NaClO₄ + requisite amount of reagent accurately weighed to give 0.004 *M* reagent concentration in final solution + 30 ml dioxan, and (iii) 5 ml of 0.64 *M* NaClO₄ + 5 ml of 0.008 *M* metal perchlorate in 0.16 *M* HClO₄ + requisite amount of accurately weighed reagent to give 0.004 *M* reagent concentration in final solution + 30 ml of dioxan. The titrations were performed in duplicate to test for reproducibility.

Proton-ligand and metal-ligand stability constants: The $\bar{n}_A$ values for the ligands were calculated by using the method of Mahnot⁴. The pK_1 and pK_2 values of these reagents were determined by half-integral method and by straight line plots of $\log \bar{n}_A/(1-\bar{n}_A)$ against *B*, and $\log (2-\bar{n}_A)/(\bar{n}_A-1)$ against *B*. Since the difference between pK_1 and pK_2 is less than 1.78 log unit, the values were better determined by least-square method.

The metal-ligand stability constants $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ were determined by half-integral method and straight line plots of $\log \bar{n}/(1-\bar{n})$ against *pL* and $\log (2-\bar{n})/(\bar{n}-1)$ against *pL*. For those metal systems where the difference between $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ was less than 1.78 log unit, the values were better determined by least-square method. The most representative values are recorded in Table 2.

Results and Discussion

The pK_1 values of ligands were examined in the light of mesomeric and inductive effects of the

substituent. The pK_1 value of 2,4-dihydroxybenzylidene phenylhydrazone is 13.21 and that of 2,4-dihydroxybenzylidene thiosemicarbazone is 11.89. In both the compounds, there is a NH group on the azomethine N-atom. In such cases, the electron density on azomethine N-atom should be higher because of lone-pair availability on the adjacent N-atom. This is reflected in their pK values which are high. However, there is a drastic change in the pK values of the two compounds. In both of them, the substituents on the NH group are electron-withdrawing. The abnormally low pK value of compound (A) could be rationalised by taking into account the electronic picture of the thione group,

For a thione group the canonical form (b) is more contributing than (a). The π -bond between C and S is very weak as it is formed by the unequal overlap of 2p-orbital of the carbon atom and the 3p-orbital of sulphur atom. Hence, the dipolar canonical form (b) is the major contributing structure. As such the thione carbon atom is more electron-deficient, and the lone-pair on the adjacent N-atom would be strongly withdrawn to carbon atom.

Four canonical structures (1, 2, 3, 4) for $-NH-C(=S)-NH_2$ part of the thiosemicarbazone can be written as

Of these, the possibility of (3) would be more likely than (4) as the electron flow from $-NH$ is more probable because it is attached to the azomethine N-atom. Thus, this phenomenon would decrease the electron density on the azomethine N-atom substantially and thereby reducing the strength of hydrogen bond, and hence, accounting for the lower pK_1 value of compound (A). In case of compound (B), the $-NH$ group is attached to electron-withdrawing phenyl ring but still the lone-pair on the N-atom may increase the electron density on the azomethine N-atom to some extent as the phenyl ring is not so a powerful electron-withdrawing group like the thione group. Hence, the pK_1 value of (B) is higher (13.21) than (A) (11.89).

The order of the stability constants for the ligand 2,4-dihydroxybenzylidene thiosemicarbazone is $UO_2^{II} > Cu^{II} > Zn^{II} > Ni^{II} > Co^{II}$, and that for 2,4-

TABLE 2—STABILITY CONSTANTS OF THE LIGANDS AND COMPLEXES

Temp. = 30 ± 0.1°, $\mu = 0.1 M$

Cation	Ligand (A)		Ligand (B)	
	log K_1	log K_2	log K_1	log K_2
H ⁺	11.89	10.24	13.21	11.27
UO ₂ ^{II}	12.75	11.81	12.46	11.15
Cu ^{II}	12.28	10.56	12.85	11.10
Ni ^{II}	11.43	10.18	9.12	—
Co ^{II}	8.23	7.00	8.20	8.08
Zn ^{II}	11.29	9.65	10.80	—

dihydroxybenzylidene phenylhydrazone, Cu^{II}>UO₂^{II}>Ni^{II}>Zn^{II}>Co^{II}.

Schiff bases are known to have chemotherapeutic activity against tubercule bacilli and other bacteria as well as against skin fungi⁵. The thiosemicarbazone of 4-acetamidobenzaldehyde (thioacetazone)⁷ was introduced for the treatment of tuberculosis in 1950. This was the first synthesised drug that approached the activity of streptomycin in experimentally induced infections in animals⁶⁻⁸. The presence of azomethine linkage in compounds has been known to decrease the toxicity considerably^{9,10}. Hence, *in vitro* antitubercular screening of these compounds was carried out against the human virulent strain of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* (H₃₇Rv) by the method of disperse-culture technique, using Kirchner's medium containing Tween-80 as dispersing agent. The antitubercular activity shown by 2,4-dihydroxybenzylidene thiosemicarbazone is 6.2 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$, while 2,4-dihydroxybenzylidene phenylhydrazone is inactive. It is felt worthwhile to study the activity of 2,4-dihydroxybenzylidene thiosemicarbazone further, and the work is in progress.

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Kinetics of Oxidation of α -Methylnaphthalene by Potassium Permanganate

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Manuscript received 2 January 1979, revised 10 April 1986, accepted 25 June 1986

THE oxidation of toluene by potassium permanganate has been extensively investigated¹. However, the oxidation of methylnaphthalene, which is a structural analogue of toluene has hitherto not been studied. In this paper we report the kinetics of oxidation of α -methylnaphthalene by permanganate in aqueous acetic acid.

Experimental

α -Methylnaphthalene (B.D.H.) was purified by fractional distillation, and collecting the fraction distilling at 240°. The other chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. The reactions were carried out at 30.0 ± 0.1° in 80% (v/v) acetic acid-water medium, unless otherwise specified. The pseudo-first order reaction was followed by quenching aliquots at definite time intervals in potassium iodide solution and titrating the liberated iodine against standard thiosulphate solution.

Product analysis: It was found that one mole of α -methylnaphthalene was required for the complete reduction of one mole of permanganate. The main product was α -naphthaldehyde. α -Naphthoic acid was formed in trace amounts (Table 1). Naphthyl alcohol, dinaphthyl and any other related

TABLE 1

Product	mole/mole KMnO ₄	M.p. (°C)	
		Found	Lit.
α -Naphthaldehyde	0.96	258	262
α -Naphthoic acid	negligible	164	161-3
2,4-Dinitrophenyl hydrazone	0.96	191	188

compounds were not detected. The products were isolated from the reaction mixture by ether extraction by following the procedure described in the oxidation of toluene by permanganate¹. The aldehyde was estimated as its 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone.

Results and Discussion

Only a trace amount of α -naphthoic acid compared to the amount of α -naphthaldehyde was obtained in the oxidation. Hence it may be concluded that the oxidation of the aldehyde proceeds at a negligible rate as compared to that of α -methylnaphthalene under the experimental conditions. This is in accordance with an earlier observation with several oxidants that side-chains attached to fused ring